

"ECOLOGY AND ENVIRONMENT" IS THE BASIS OF HUMAN HEALTH

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Abstract. *Based on the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-No.5024 dated April 21, 2017 "On improving the state management system in the field of ecology and environmental protection" and resolution PR-76 of December 30, 2021 "On measures to organize the activities of state bodies in the field of environmental protection and environmental control" "Ecology and Environment" June 5 was designated as the International Day of Environmental Protection. As part of the celebration of this day, the UN informs the international community about the environmental problems that are relevant worldwide and calls on the peoples of the world to solve these problems. "Ecology and Environment" states that awareness and conscious engagement of each individual is one of the most important issues in strengthening the ecological situation, and studies the basis of human health.*

Keywords: *biosphere, population, world population, lithosphere, photosynthesis, insecticide, troposphere, herbicide, acaricide, stratosphere, un, world ocean, carbon dioxide, oxygen.*

Introduction. "Ecology and environment" is a special shell of the earth, formed as a result of long biochemical currents under the influence of solar energy in biosphere. The biosphere includes the lower layers of the atmosphere, that is, the troposphere up to 15-20 km high and the lower part of the stratosphere, the deepest depressions of the World Ocean up to 11 km deep, and the lithosphere up to 4.5 km below the surface of the earth. Man is also a component of the biosphere. Every year, at least 6 and a half million people die in the world due to diseases caused by pollution of "Ecology and environment". The world population is increasing day by day. According to the data provided by the UN on the number of the planet's population, at the beginning of 2022 the world population was 7.8 billion people.

The population of our planet is increasing by 82 million people every year. By the end of 2050, the world population will reach 9.7 billion people. This was announced at the 52nd session of the Commission on Population and Development, which began at the UN headquarters in New York. In particular, the world population is predicted to reach 11 billion people at the end of this century. But 1.3 billion people do not have the opportunity to eat enough. Most of them are suffering from famine. In order to ensure food safety on a global scale, it is necessary to begin to moderate its consumption, to practice frugality and to give great importance to this issue.

On April 17 of this year, by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Strategy for implementation of work related to solid household waste in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the period 2019-2028" and "Action program for the implementation of the strategy for the implementation of work related to solid household waste in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2028" have been approved on "Ecology and environment". Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 21, 2017 PD- No. 5024 "On improving the state management

system in the field of ecology and environmental protection", resolutions PR- No.2915 "On measures to ensure the activities of the State Committee for Ecology and Environmental Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and PR-No. 2916 "On measures to fundamentally improve and develop the system of implementation of work related to household waste in 2017-2021" on "Ecology and environment" have been approved, the field of ecology and environmental protection has been fundamentally improved.

In the process of growth and development, living organisms interact with the environment in which they live, and this process leads to environmental changes. For example: Plants absorb solar energy and carbon dioxide from the air, absorb water and mineral substances from the soil, carry out the process of photosynthesis in their bodies, and produce organic substances. They release oxygen to the environment, provide nutrition for various animals and humans due to organic matter and breathing due to oxygen. As a result of the evolutionary development of living organisms, very complex relations between nature and its organisms, geological and biological processes arise in nature. Since the emergence of man as the highest product of millions of years of evolutionary development, he has been closely connected with nature.

At the time of Aristotle, about 500 plant and 454 animal species were identified, while at present, 2 million species and forms of them have been identified. Man is changing the earth and its surface very quickly, i.e., new artificial seas are being created, he harnessed atomic energy, learned to use sunlight to fly at the speed of sound and light, and establish communications. Man began to take a lot of coal, oil, gas and other mineral resources from nature, and began to show his negative impact on the environment, that is, along with the fact that he receives the necessary items that are consumed, used in the farm, as a result of the increase in the production of harmful and dirty chemicals, the physical and chemical impact on the environment increased. As a result of such negative factors, in the next 30-40 years, many species of plants and animals are disappearing from the earth.

A global approach includes consideration of the following issues of human ecology:

1. The number of separate communities of people and the whole of humanity.
2. Age and gender composition of teams.
3. Nutrition characteristics of people of each period, calorie content of food, methods of its preparation.
4. Type of labor activity, mechanisms and tools, energy sources used in households.
5. Cultural and hygiene skills.
6. Socio-economic well-being and human development.
7. Analysis of the environment.
8. Customer service and problem management.

The same problems are included among the tasks that human ecology solves.

In the works on human ecology, issues related to the life processes of the population with climate, natural waters, soil cover, vegetation, dangerous natural phenomena and biogeochemical conditions are constantly discussed. Human ecologists use information on population genetics, environmental genetics, genetic diseases and anomalies in humans, environmental physiology, immunodeficiency states, allergology, environmental toxicology, drug toxicology, radioecology, and bio-cybernetics. Anthropecologists make extensive use of materials from the following branches of medicine: history of medicine and health history, biological basis of medicine, clinical medicine, epidemiology of infectious and non-infectious diseases, general hygiene, social hygiene,

public hygiene and environmental hygiene, food hygiene and radiation hygiene. Human ecology has adopted some methodological principles, methodological approaches and research methods. Epidemiology of infectious diseases is a science that studies the laws of the epidemic process and develops methods of combating human infectious diseases. Epidemiology of non-communicable diseases is interpreted as a method of studying the spread of non-communicable diseases among the population using statistical indicators. Human ecology is closely related to many social sciences.

Demography has the deepest connections with human ecology, as both disciplines study populations in similar ways. There is a close relationship between them. Anthropoecology and sociology study the interrelationship of various social phenomena and social behavior of people. Human ecology is closely related to the following areas of economic science: world natural resources, world food situation, international social division of labor, distribution of productive forces, economic regionalization, economics of urbanization and cities, health economics, ecological economics, recreational economics. Considering the interrelation between anthropoecology and other scientific fields, it is appropriate to dwell on such important sciences as district plan and urban planning.

The following research areas are relevant to the interests of human ecology: theoretical and scientific foundations of district planning and urban planning, planning and development of regions and large areas, planning and development of cities and settlements, urban agglomerations. Studies of human ecology use the historical method, as well as information from the work of archaeologists, ethnographers, and ethnologists. The logic of anthropoecological research suggests the need for close cooperation between human ecology and psychology. The methods used in human ecology, the systematic approach cover most anthropoecological researches, because the person himself and a certain studied community are part of the system due to the universal interdependence of living nature elements. Much attention is paid to the creation of cadastres, which include the assessment of natural, social, economic, political, ecological, hygienic and other factors, which affect the life activities of the population. In order to solve scientific and practical problems in human ecology, research is carried out at different spatial levels, which can be divided into three main levels - local, regional and global. Each of them has its own research characteristics, and the depth and level of disclosed processes are unique to this level. Each level has its own cartographic scale, both cartographic sources and cartographic design of the final results of the research have been developed in the sciences of anthropological problems of research, are solved using the methods of data collection, which served as the basis for the formation of human ecology. These methods include assessment, modeling, mapping, regionalization, and forecasting. A habitat assessment is a comparison of the unknown with the known.

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